

Innovative Best Practices in Academic Libraries

Jayashree Sriramulu Saroja

Abstract:- This paper is principally focused introducing importance of the innovative best practices to be followed by academic libraries. This paper includes what's best today might not be the most effective tomorrow. Therefore, the innovative best practice is an attitude, an approach or a philosophy supported the need for continuous learning and improvement within the NAAC Committee, there are mention separate section for the library and library and data services, so library could be a most significant part of support for entire range of educational activities on an academic institution. "Books are to be used, every reader his or her book, every book its reader"– S. R. Ranganathan.

Keywords:- Academic Libraries, NAAC, Library Services, ICT, Information Literacy, User Education.

I. INTRODUCTION

Innovative best practices in academic library could also be viewed mutually that enhances user satisfaction contributing to full realization of one's academic potential. Effective academic libraries enhance student learning outcomes by providing a variety of programs, services and resources which support teaching and learning. It encourages students' reading practices. Document prepared by NAAC for Best practices in academic libraries says, "Best practices is also innovative and be a philosophy, policy strategy, program, process or practice that solves an issue, or create new opportunities and positively impact on organizations, NAAC developed a group of best practices followed in academic libraries and dotted the purpose within the following four broad areas: a) Resource Management and Administration of Library b) Collection & Services c) Extent the user services d) use of technology.

Academic libraries of every kind are witnessing change in last twenty years thus far till nineteenth century, importance given to storage of documents. In the present decades open access era libraries have undergone changes not only in about what a library is and the way it should be; but within the form and various types of holdings method of storage, organization and dissemination of document information. Innovative practices or Best practices are the standard enhancing plan of action, services or functions picked by a tutorial library. The libraries must exercise best practices to satisfy this day challenges using ICT to fulfill the employment of the services and resources from the library. The innovative practices are nothing but the standards of the simplest practices academic institutions. Innovative practices are ever changing and continuous process and are always the results of identification, feedback, innovative and knowledge oriented always expected agreeable to documentation. Academic library expects

transparent accountability, affordable and accessible to the stakeholders.

Presently, academic libraries don't seem to be only disseminating the data they contain within the campus library but beyond them also Dr. S. R. Ranganathan's five laws catalyzed the the event and transformation of libraries. Most all academic libraries have the power of Internet resources which supplement the print collection of the library. These changes are substantial. The matter with us is that several changes we come upon, we immediately take it as part of routine Internet facility helps in saving rime, repetition and redundancy, intermission and delays. We are able to communicate with information service providers within no time just case of only problem. Changing or adding new things to existing collection of services.

Given the actual fact, the library will be considered because the backbone of any academic institution, because it not just supplements the activities of an establishment, but also plays a awfully significant role in supplementing students and faculties. Libraries gain their strength and recognition from the richness of their resources collected over a period of your time.

Librarians are adopting innovative or best practices within the academic libraries taking the technology of the time of their advantage and by experience. Librarian will should study the potential of library software as many features are still not known to us.

The academic Library may be implemented innovative or best practices in terms of using Standard Policies and Procedures of all library activities which as follows:

- a) Library automation using ICT tools and library software. Using software for the educational library operations has the following advantages:
 - It satisfies Dr. S. R. Ranganathan's the fourth law of library and knowledge science i.e., Save the time of the user and also its corollary, save the time of the staff. It reduces the period to be taken for routine functions of the library. The productive work is utilized.
- b) At the start of each year, an orientation programme was being given to the first year students.
- c) Initiating to fresher conducting information Literacy skills into learning activities
- d) Library newsletter / Information Alert Services / Pamphlets. News Groups. This helps to marketing the library resources and services. It makes the utilization of library a simple way public city.
- e) Display newspaper clippings on the board

- f) Display of employment information / Career / Study in Aboard / Services
- g) Displaying new arrival books/journals on the library bulletin board and circulating a listing to different in faculty department
- h) Compiling student's ratio of attendance statistics (graphic) on the library bulletin board further as faculty departments.
- i) Students suggestions box for timely response
- j) Internet facilities to different users stream/course
- k) Library website inclusion of comprehensive information about the resource library, facility and services, prospectus, question bank
- l) Organizing Critical Review from Books / Magazine / Newspaper
- m) Organizing General Knowledge Quiz / Debate on Current Awareness / Essay Competition
- n) Collecting Users Feedback through survey periodically
- o) Conducting Book Exhibition and Book Talks
- p) Best Library User Award Annually for college students. Awards are always a motivating factor. It acts an incentive for a habitual user of the library. Such kind of awards attracts the scholars towards the library and helps in not only boosting the usage of the library by the scholars but are effective in making him/her a habitual user of the library and a lifelong learner.
- q) Mobile Access Technology on College Library App
- r) Conducting Workshop / Training / Conference and Seminars
- s) Publishing College Magazine / Library News letter
- t) Development of a library web page including all the services and necessary information. Web based instruction (FAQ's)
- u) Feedback form stockholders through scientifically designed and analyzed questionnaire, at least quarterly.
- v) Vendor's participation
- w) Library Brochure
- x) One – on – one Appointments
- y) Library Tour
- z) Virtual Reference Desk / Ask Your Librarian

II. BEST PRACTICES IN LIBRARY SERVICES WITH INNOVATIVE WAY

To ensure academic excellence of both teachers and students relevant text books, reference books, standard journals, E-Journals are being procured by the library. The exciting new highlights the latest innovative services and programs in academic libraries. Now a day's rapidly increasing use of smart phones, tablets in the library to access information, as well as the growing role of social media, blogging, and e-learning instruction, the identities of libraries are being transformed. Every function of the library, including Students service, can be improved with technology. Provide right information to right user at right time at right place in this digital time.

➤ *Library Services in Mobile*

Users work in an academic library looking go thru mobile, or they are seeking ideas for specific apps to create or implement, they will find user-friendly and approachable manner, with examples drawn from experience. It will inspire and support the integration of mobile technologies on all scales into academic library.

Social Media in Libraries: The innovative use of Twitter, blogs, Facebook, Pinterest, Social Catalogs etc., Social Media policy provides creative ways to reach teens and others who were not using the library, so librarians and faculty would find this valuable information on this adoption.

➤ *Customer Service in Libraries*

Library different from a bookstore, and some will likely respond with "Computers" or "Programs" customer service policies and models in any library can both adapt and be proud of to micro-approaches that emphasize offering excellent user-focused technology planning, with patrons in mind, Web 2.0 tools to connect users with the library, establishing good service delivery chains, and making library excellent.

➤ *E-Learning in Libraries*

Online credit-based instruction for undergraduates, digital reference, information-literacy, e-learning collaboration, open-source software that supports online interactive learning, screen casting for instruction and reference, and many more innovative services. Definitely it will be worth the time consuming to read and reap some ideas for developing e-instruction for library patrons.

III. CONCLUSION

Innovative or best practices in academic are the quality enhancing strategies, services or functions picked by an institution the possible highest number of target groups with available resources in best possible ways. The present day challenges using ICT and LMS to meet the information requirements of the user's community and to maximum the utilization of the services and resources of the library. The stakeholders of the college must realize the problems that are facing by the libraries and do the needful to solve them on a priority basis at the same time, quality aspects come from commitment and dedication of the library professionals of the academic colleges.

It is suggested to NAAC that the innovative best practices followed in libraries operating in colleges should have been taken into account. There are areas which we not been able to find out as innovative best practices. A few examples of such areas are index to periodicals, real time reference services, preparation of various statistics of the use of e-resources and many other areas.

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